

Cosmopolitanism in De la Mare's "The Listeners" and Mahon's "Afterlives": A Comparative Study

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Abstract

Cosmopolitanism is one of the most controversial ideologies dealt with English literature. It focuses on multiple characteristic features a man, modern and contemporary, may carry. Features like being cosmopolite or world citizen, placeless, patriot, and free which could protect him or her from being alienated, estranged, fearful, and undignified. It has some similarities with other concepts like universalism, multiculturalism, and humanism. The need for being a cosmopolite comes from the harsh circumstances of modern and contemporary lives presented in literature due to wrong policies, vicious globalization, and social injustice. This research paper deals with the concept of cosmopolitanism socially and philosophically and applies it to two poems: Walter De la Mare's "The Listeners" (1912) and Derek Mahon's "Afterlives" (1975) modern and contemporary respectively. The paper also aims at tracing the concept in both poems and comparing them thoroughly in order to show how it is employed, expressed, and concluded. In addition, the paper answers the questions: What is the use of being a world citizen? What makes a man be so? How does a cosmopolite feel outside and inside his country?

1. Introduction

The cosmopolite or the world citizen is generally known as a person who feels at home wherever he or she goes. Such a person could cross the borders without feeling a stranger. In order to fully comprehend the term, one has to look at the term cosmopolitanism first. Generally, cosmopolitanism was "derived from Ancient Greek as 'citizen of the world' and the word involves receptive and open attitude toward the others" (Kendall, Ian, and Zlatko 1). It is defined as a "devotion to humanity and detachment from local bonds" (Spencer 2).

Historically speaking, cosmopolitanism as a concept has existed for a long time. It appeared in Ancient Greek with a critical role politically and socially. At the beginning of the eighteenth century, Immanuel Kant (1724–1804), a modern philosopher, believed that a "cosmopolitan condition" means: "violation of rights in one part of the world is felt everywhere" (107-8). To Frederick Hegel (1770–1831), a nineteenth-century creator of "dialectic logic," cosmopolitanism is significant for a human being who "counts as such because he is a human being, not because he is a Jew, Catholic, Protestant, German, Italian, etc." (209).

Sociologically, Emile Durkheim (1858–1917) who has been one of the fathers of sociology has considered cosmopolitanism in the name of "world patriotism." According to Durkheim, "societies can have their pride, not in being the greatest or the wealthiest, but in being the most just, the best organized and in possessing the best moral constitution" (74-5). Lastly, Ulrich Beck's point of view has been about the fact that people who are living in a global village have the same universal problems. Furthermore, cosmopolitanism, in Spencer's point of view, "remains tainted by the pejorative connotations of utopianism, escapism and condescension" (3).

It is significant to be familiar with some of the characteristic features of cosmopolites so that one can figure them out clearly. "Cosmopolites," to Spencer, "are viewed as free-floating and ethereal creatures: recklessly, deludedly and perhaps even selfishly indifferent to the travails and responsibilities of those who are confined through choice or necessity to the local sphere" (3). As "free-floating and ethereal," they are free all the time in choosing when where and how to live. They are indifferent to the responsibilities of being confined, restricted, and limited. Thus, they believe themselves to be global rather than local.

People like these do mean to be uprooted in their societies, rather, they have a sense of belongingness to every place they visit or even imagined. In this respect, Craig Calhoun, an American sociologist, believes that one has to promote a sense of mutual and cosmopolitan solidarity through the community he or she belongs to. Calhoun also argues that "Community is not just inherited, it is made and remade" (98). Consequently, social solidarity is not just caused by people's inherited identities and interests but also by shared participation in the public sphere. That is to say, cosmopolitanism can be regarded as a process of human development intellectually, sociologically, and culturally and a fact as well. To sum it up, Spencer defines cosmopolitanism in a very short-cut disposition, saying:

[It is the] one characterised by self-awareness, by a penetrating sensitivity to the world beyond one's immediate milieu, and by an enlarged sense of moral and political responsibility to individuals and groups outside one's local or national community (4).

One of the most central concerns about cosmopolitanism is its necessity in people's lives. Spencer believes that cosmopolitanism exists by the global reach of problems that require some solutions democratically so that it could make them legitimate and effective through global allegiances and solidarities (5). For Spencer, some of these global problems include

ethnic nationalism; underdevelopment and exploitation [...]; environmental degradation and the jeopardising of humankind's very survival on earth by the changing climate; the abuse of human rights; the unequal distribution of resources; [and] the proliferation of deadly weapons (5).

Because of these problems and many others, one has to think realistically about the solutions; cosmopolitanism is definitely one of them since it calls for a democratic settlement and political mechanisms that will hopefully be in harmony with the worldly citizen who is in a constant struggling against the numerous snags currently facing humanity. That is why cosmopolitanism, to use Pheng Cheah's words, is an "expansive form of solidarity that is attuned to democratic principles without the restriction of territorial borders" (19).

Furthermore, Spencer proposes some principles to identify the cosmopolite with: "solidarity, community, democracy and human rights." The cosmopolite is the one who moves from the globalization and inequality to much more democratic and equal in nature (13). Similarly, Jackie Stacey adds good intentions in dealing with others as a complementary principle. In this sense, she argues that "cosmopolitanism often posits a self that is transparent, accessible and fully intelligible to ourselves and others" (34). Stacey proves her claim by posing two important questions. By doing so, she seeks no answers, rather, she stresses the aim of being a cosmopolite and how the cosmopolite looks like. She wonders: "What if one's own sense of openness to difference appears to others as closure, assimilation or appropriation? [...] What if the projection of world citizenship is a blended panhumanity that violently erases difference instead of recognising it?" (34).

From a political point of view, being a cosmopolite means that a sense of worldliness should prevail. William Smith, a political theorist, has claimed that

[T]he political project of cosmopolitanism requires a corresponding account of cosmopolitan virtue that identifies the qualities and dispositions that make individuals aware of their cosmopolitan obligations, more likely to discharge them, and more effective in doing so (42).

Smith conveys a concluding message that stresses on the cosmopolitan citizens being part of the world. He is also promoting an insight into cosmopolitan ambitions by applying the principles of justice and solidarity. In Smith's words, "this element of worldliness should be interpreted as a strong desire to cultivate the cosmopolitan promise latent in the world as it is with a view to promoting a more cosmopolitan future" (46).

Edward Said, another critic, exemplified the disposition of worldliness, by saying: "To be worldly means being articulate, persuasive, daring, independent and troublesome. It also enjoins one to campaign for the general [...] application of fundamental rights" (55). Thus, the idea of worldliness allows people to think about a lost idea urgently. Likewise, being a cosmopolite means that you are looking for "local and larger than local" realities, "ethnocentric and relativist" places and "particularism and universalism" interpretations (Ribeiro 2842). Accordingly, cosmopolitanism is a concept improved by the elites to expose some misunderstandings and prejudices about equality about it. Different points of view and definitions can be found to identify the real meaning of such a concept which has been changed since ancient times through the current time in multiple levels. To be a cosmopolite, one has to spread the spirit of democracy, altruism, brotherhood, equality, and worldliness across the borders without being uprooted.

De la Mare's Haunted Place

As one of the greatest English poets, specifically the Georgian ones, Walter de la Mare has two special gifts: supernaturalism and mysteriousness, two elements seem to be derived from the Romantic Poetry. These two features are really linked to how the modern man may feel everywhere and every time: estranged and alone. A believer in the supernatural and mysterious, de la Mare, through his poetry, keeps "revealing the ordinary in whimsical colours, of catching the commonplace off its guard; [...] his] sense of the supernatural, of the fantastic other-world [...] lies on the edges of our consciousness" (Untermeyer 89).

The universe, to de la Mare, is a spectacular and exhilarating place where anything may happen at any time. In this regard, Lord Dunsany calls de la Mare's world as "the haunted Land of de la Mare" for the latter is the master, the interpreter, the priest and the poet of this mysterious, incomprehensible and impulsive world. de la Mare also believes that the world is alive with the supernatural; life is a rainbow-like bubble of magic blown on the breath of reality (Duffin 66-68).

Although de la Mare's poetry depends on imagination when interpreting, it is "the creation of a mind brooding: upon its earthly pilgrimage" (Reid 11) in which one feels that he or she is in physical and spiritual journeys. So, from the poet's point of view, people are all travellers and listeners simultaneously. de la Mare truly mistrusts the intellect, still, he believes that life is meaningful. Life, to him, is not "a cosmic joke because

he knew that someone or something would have had to have played it.” What concerns de la Mare is the “timeless self,” which “must beat against its walls in vain.” This conception also explains his preoccupation with death, nostalgia, exile, dreams, the supernatural, children, and nature (McCrosson 51). Furthermore, Dyson, in his “Walter de la Mare’s ‘The Listeners,’” assumes that

De la Mare’s world is a world of one; there are no relationships in it, either to people, or to places, or to time. The Traveller might be Any Man, the episode Any Time and Any Place, as in a sense they are (151).

Walter De la Mare’s “The Listeners” (1920) has a dreamlike tone and a bleak mood. Its “scene is unlocalised, yet remarkably clear and precise too in the details, as dreams often are.” Its setting includes a moonlight derived adapted from the Romantic Poetry, “a setting for experience heightened beyond the commonplace” (Dyson 151). The main character in this poem is the traveller whose questions from the very beginning till the end asserts his struggle against two important concepts: the supernatural and loneliness. The last one is one of the most common terms felt in the twentieth century, at least at the time of the poem: “it has a social setting-it is the loneliness of the saint or the sinner, the king or the beggar. The genius or the half-wit, the hero or the coward, the betrayed or the betrayer, or what you will” (Dyson 152). In other words, through its tone, setting, character, and themes, the poem discloses the elements of how to feel like a cosmopolite.

“The Listeners” presents an image of a world citizen whose universal message is seen as both individual and cosmopolitan. The poem, in brief, describes a traveller who has come to an isolated house to knock at its moonlit door. The traveller came to keep an unnamed promise, knocking more than one time, but he never gets any response. The house, he knocks at, is inhabited by a host of phantom listeners whose silence adds a sense of mystery to the place. The poem is engaged with depicting a timeless man in a universe that seems to be “greater than him” (Jason). The traveller could not find any harmony with the natural world where he lives. As a result, he feels disturbed and anxious. He tries to break the silence around him by knocking at the door harder and harder and as he is knocking, he shouts:

‘Is there anybody there?’ said the Traveller,
Knocking on the moonlit door;
And his horse in the silence champed the grasses
Of the forest’s ferny floor: (1-4 “The Listeners”)

The noise he makes is accompanied by the sound of the horse while champing the grasses, and the sound of the hooves of the horse that acts as a means to defeat that silence. De la Mare keeps describing the bleak house and the traveller’s second attempt of knocking and inquiring. A bird flew up out of the turret or tower. The image of the turret suggests that the building is not an ordinary house, but a castle-like home. The overwhelming sense of mystery captures the readers’ attention and leads to a point related to the man’s mysterious future in this world. Similarly, the poet declares:

And a bird flew up out of the turret,
Above the Traveller’s head:
And he smote upon the door again a second time;
‘Is there anybody there?’ he said. (5-8 “The Listeners”)

Even when the setting in this poem is homely, de la Mare also introduces his characters and scenes to readers strangely and outlandishly. For instance, “The houses are secret and irregular, full of dark, nooks and dusty accumulated junk; quaint ornaments; forgotten books and dim portraits” (Cecil 4).

Describing the mysterious house, in “The Listeners,” by phrases like “leaf-fringed sill”; “the lone” and “the still house”; which includes “shadowiness”; “dark stair” and “empty hall,” de la Mare personalizes the house and regards it as a common place in the deepest sense. Undoubtedly, readers have that sense at one time when they visited ancient buildings and felt the presence of those who were there long ago. Accordingly, de la Mare artistically expresses these presences with more reality than most other poets are likely to do (McCrosson 58). In this sense, the poet in the following lines elucidates:

But no one descended to the traveller,
No head from the leaf-fringed sill
learned over and looked into his grey eyes
where he stood perplexed and still. (9-12 “The Listeners”)

Being nameless, the traveller is a person who travels from one place into another. He came from afar history to keep an unnamed promise. His mysterious presence gives a possibility to read his character as a symbol for humankind as a whole. He is a cosmopolitan figure who came from unknown time to approach an isolated house in the forest and is desperate to finish his journey with satisfaction (Jason).

It is also thought that the unknown traveller is an example of returning the dead's spirit. Similarly, a departed soul returns to the house where it lived before dying, knocks and speaks to the dwellers of the house. de la Mare's world is full of imagination that takes people to other places. In this sense, J.B. Priestley observed that such a world is regarded as the region which lies "between the conscious mind of our time and the collective unconscious" (Priestley 18). In addition, the supernatural is considered as another reason for "Other Worldliness" and "the mystical temperament" in the poetry of Walter de la Mare (Sturgeon 76).

As a questing spirit, annoyed by the boundaries of physical consciousness, de la Mare strains out into the unknown through reflecting such a trait in his questing traveller who has explored "Man's journey through the Waste Land of the spirit." However, "the poignancy of his utterance is just that there is no answering certitude, however near at times, Man feels he is to apprehending one" (Peschmann 130). The unresponsive phantom of listeners is different from the traveller's coming. Their indifference to the traveller's concern with an unnamed message he carries refers symbolically to man's historical quest for understanding the truth of his own existence. Likewise, the description of the listeners inside the house clarifies the ideas above:

But only a host of phantom listeners
That dwelt in the lone house then
Stood listening in the quiet of the moonlight
To that voice from the world of men: (13-16 "The Listeners")

Furthermore, the traveller stands for the cosmopolite whose quest in all situations is to discover some solution to life mystery. However, although it is accurately stated that to de la Mare "the whole of life is a journey; he is acutely aware of our pilgrimage towards some "mysterious bourne"; he is, himself, the constant traveller" (Sack-ville-West 27). The traveller, confirms an awareness of the transience of existence which almost approaches despair in a relatively bleak one. In the following lines, the poet mixes two important elements, "strangeness" and "stillness" in order to highlight the whole situation between the traveller and the listeners:

Stood thronging the faint moonbeams on the dark stair
that goes down to the empty hall
Harkening in an air stirred and shaken
By the lonely Traveller's call. (17-20 "The Listeners")

The traveller who expected to be greeted by the dwellers of the house receives no answer though he tries to strike with force perhaps for some reason he expected that there would be someone to hand him the unknown message. The traveller remains alone standing in his place. This situation is seen as a point of crossing the time and place and maybe his voice to the last one from the world of men. The traveller is metaphorically the last survivor on earth whose only message resonates with the idea of "a human search for a purpose that is ultimately thwarted" (Jason).

Feeling so strange, the traveller knows that there are "phantoms" inside the house listening to his words. Nonetheless, the quiet house "answer[s] his cry." He is provoked to try again by knocking on the door once more and with more force. He makes his knocks "Louder." After he lifts his head up to the window and calls out, he asks that the presence he feels inside the house "Tell them I came."

And he felt in his heart their strangeness,
Their stillness answering his cry,
While his horse moved, cropping the dark turf
'Neath the starred and leafy sky;
For he suddenly smote on the door, even
Louder, and lifted his head:- (21-26 "The Listeners")

As no answer is heard, the traveller says another phrase, "That I kept my word." The promise that he has made is one of the reasons that made him repeat the knocking. No reactions came out of the house. Readers become so curious that they will not be satisfied easily, however, de la Mare's narrative is apparently crafty. The final lines of this section describe how the words "he spake" fell through. In this respect, these "words have a finality, heroic yet forlorn, which resonates against the other finality of the silence, and lingers with it in unresolved enigma as the poem passes into our memory" (Dyson 152).

'Tell them I came, and no one answered,
That I kept my word,' he said.
Never the least stir made the listeners,
Though every word he spake (27-30 "The Listeners")

The traveller who represents a searching soul is forced to leave alone. The listeners who represent the unresponsive divine guidance to man's misunderstanding of the truth of himself, are unknowable. They are thus analogous to the nautical force which is indifferent to man's destiny and takes no action to give an answer to the

repeated question. The traveller is a functional figure who acts like a man with an essential purpose. He comes from no time and place to expose his dissatisfaction with this world to the listeners. He in this regard is an agent of all humankind and the only one alive to keep man's promise. At the end of the poem, the poet makes a shift in place from the traveller outside the house into the listeners inside. They listen to the sound of the "plunging hoofs" fading away into the forest with no response to the noise made by the traveller and his horse.

The end is left open indicating the strangeness of the listeners' vague situation and the traveller's imperfect quest for establishing harmony with the natural world:

Fell echoing through the shadowiness of the still house
 From the one man left awake:
 Ay, they heard his foot upon the stirrup,
 And the sound of iron on stone,
 And how the silence surged softly backward,
 When the plunging hoofs were gone. (31-36 "The Listeners")

What makes the poem effective is its overtones of a ghost story rather than the narrative itself. The adventure of some traveller who is heroically challenging a heedless universe is asserted through silence and mystery which are expressed more creepily; the symbolism of man's courage facing the cryptic riddle of life is more memorably (Untermeyer 89). Symbolically speaking, the poem, through the traveller's question: "Is there anybody there?" and setting,

has all the material for an exploration of the meaning of existence itself. . . . The quest itself is familiar, guided by loyalties which might or might not be honoured, to ends not always known. The very absence of information about the 'them' this particular Traveller has come to meet enables us to feel all the more the relevance to our own dark future meetings (Dyson 153).

Mahon's Cosmopolitan Place

Primarily, Mahon's internationalism is a method for self-examination and self-understanding. He expresses his emotions and feelings towards his country through the universal aspects his poetry offers. He also looks at the question of artistic commitment and the validity of poetry in a new light. In this respect, Tinley, in his article, proclaims that "Mahon's objectivity and philosophical detachment are methods of understanding." Commenting on Mahon's interest in international and cosmopolitan issues, Tinley also says that Mahon's "attraction to international art is both a means of giving himself creative space and a way of investigating his own frailties in a wider cultural and social context" (111). So, the comparison is so significant to the person who wants to have more opportunities in proving himself, on the one hand, and to discover the weak points and work on them on the other hand.

Moreover, it is likely that Mahon either personalizes and internalizes his poems to correlate himself as a poet and an artist with universalization. Hence, Mahon uses a technique by which he paradoxically enables objectivity to evaluate one's past to fully elaborate his own philosophy of cosmopolitanism. Similarly, Tinley states:

The international aspect of Mahon's writing is thus both an intrinsic characteristic of his poetry and a means to an end. [His poems] reveal a two-way process at work in which the cosmopolitan, enlightened voice is interchangeable with an uncertain, doubtful one.... His work raises and suggests answers to questions about art and society, just as his Europeanism confronts notions about national literature and redefines its constituencies. Watching us as a citizen of the world he is waiting to come home (117).

Mahon's life train passes through and stops in many different stations. Various cities around the world such as London, Dublin, New York, and Belfast are among the places where Mahon lived or even moved into. Mahon expresses his poetic international perspectives by considering himself as a poet rather than an Irish poet. Likewise, in an interview with Harriet Cooke, Mahon said that Irish writers "should be judged by London, New York standards" (10). Such actions and claims refer to Mahon's belief in being a cosmopolite.

Mahon's interests in world literature, Latin and French, for example, and general themes like identity, exile, and apocalypse seem to be reflected in his poetry, according to Bill Tinley, to prove his dislike to the literature that "does not look beyond its immediate environment" and "does not search for the major theme among the minor ones." At the same time, Mahon "is attracted to an art which transcends its localism without compromising the integrity of its sources" (106).

In addition, Mahon reflected his historical and personal experiences throughout his work which "is certainly related to the political crisis of a period in which the relationship between Britain and Ireland has been profoundly affected by the Northern Irish problem." Accordingly, Mahon relates "imaginatively to the North, to Ireland and the rest of the world in such a period, when violence was endemic" to take responsibility for expressing his own problems and make them the world ones (Brown 133).

The title of the poem is so overwhelming that any reader becomes curious about people's afterlives. What will happen after a person leaves his country? Will he die? Are we going to be immortal by reflecting on our situation there? Will be able to meet our lovely people like those back at home? Such questions come to minds first. Derek Mahon tries his best to answer such questions and many others on his unique and cosmopolitan way. Mahon begins with a controversial dedication to James Simmons whose class refers to his situation. The poem is divided into two parts: the first one leads to the second one and serves as an answer to questions raised in the first one.

Beginning with topics like waking up, Mahon attracts the readers' attention to the importance of being alive again whether you are inside or outside your country:

I wake in a dark flat
To the soft roar of the world.
Pigeons neck on the white
Roofs as I draw the curtains
And look out over London
Rain-fresh in the morning light. ("Afterlives" 1-6)

Stanza one shows how strange the poet feels because he woke in a dark flat. This is the first place which shows that he is not in his own place. Although dark and noisy, the new place is so soft for him in comparison with his own place. The word "world" is a direct reference to universal, cosmopolitan and international concepts. Mahon refers to peace by mentioning pigeons as they are perching on white roofs outside his window. Two things he misses in his own country peace and purity as represented by pigeons and white snow. According to Mahon, London is the whole world through which he can see light and rain definitely missing in his own country due to a number of reasons.

Mahon refers to London as the bright reason he and his people aspire to live in. Stanza two gives two main reasons to consider London as an ideal place to live in for some time at least:

This is our element, the bright
Reason on which we rely
For the long-term solutions.
The orators yap, and guns
Go off in a back street;
But the faith doesn't die ("Afterlives" 7-12)

It is the long-term solution for his problems, mainly the political ones, as well as the faith that exists regardless of the sounds of guns and orations backyard. Contradictorily, London has its own problems, though they are not worse than the old ones back home. As if he wanted to say we as Irish have our own problems which are somehow similar to yours, however, you follow reason, faith, and solutions to overcome them; we don't:

That in our time these things
Will amaze the literate children
In their non-sectarian schools
And the dark places be
Ablaze with love and poetry
When the power of good prevails. ("Afterlives" 13-18)

The concepts, mentioned in stanza three, will definitely be amazing in the eyes of Irish children who are regarded as literate and aspire not to be in a sectarian school. Mahon's ambition is so high that he wants his country schools void of sectarianism brought by politics. He also wishes that dark places, like prisons, would be alight with love and poetry. In one condition, the power of good prevails especially with the role of spreading love through poetry. Hence, the power of words is affirmed in order to express one's ideas.

Generally speaking, the points of view introduced in Mahon's poems refer to interchangeability between subjectivity and objectivity. For instance, "I" and "you" become substitutable especially when Mahon "either assumes a new, ironical identity or addresses himself from afar as a way of investigating and understanding the experiences he commits." (Burton 347). Mahon uses an exceptional technique that is noticeably initiated in "Afterlives" where the pronouns "I" and "we," are so obvious throughout the poem. The pronoun "I" reveals "the confusion of existential division": for it is used to refer to either staying or leaving. This technique does not show that

Mahon is incapable of empathy or that subjectivity is relinquished completely. Exhausted or not, Mahon rediscovers here an inspirational place from which to journey imaginatively and dream of an inviting, welcoming elsewhere (Burton 347).

Thus, the inconclusive ending suggests that the call of this elsewhere is too strong and that there is more journeying involved for the peripatetic poet. In stanza four, another comparison among social classes is clarified:

What middle-class shits we are
 To imagine for one second
 That our privileged ideals
 Are divine wisdom, and the dim
 Forms that kneel at noon
 In the city not ourselves. (“Afterlives” 19-24)

Being a middle-class man, like Simmon, Mahon is so proud of himself and his ideals that are not a pearl of divine wisdom rather an imagination for a second a thought that cannot be achieved. All the bad intentions can be seen reflected in the city, not in one’s self. Mahon positions his disenchantment within a historical and political situation. That is to say, living in London is outlined by returning to Belfast (Waters 103).

Although Mahon in the centre, his hometown, he considered the peripheral, other countries, as “a vantage point which opens on empty desolation that cuts human pride down to size” (Brown 135). Mahon sees the landscape as substantial in reflecting his cosmopolitan inclinations for it “can serve as more than the symbolic expression of a vision of negation, of the rootless consciousness in an empty universe” (Brown 135).

In part two which represents the answers for the inquiries mentioned in part one of the first three stanzas, Mahon begins describing his journey back home:

I am going home by sea
 For the first time in years.
 Somebody thumbs a guitar
 On the dark deck, while a gull
 Dreams at the masthead,
 The moon-splashed waves exult. (“Afterlives” 25-30)

Mahon went back home and began reflecting on his way back by the sea. For him, this is the first time after five years to meet his country. He describes the ship, gull, and waves beautifully. In his poetry, precisely in “Afterlives,” Mahon persistently devotes a big amount of attention to “the places he chooses as subjects in England and Ireland and in the world at large with this poignant atmosphere of certain loss” (Brown 137). Alienated from his native place, exile, homelessness, loneliness, the defining conditions of modernity can be felt in Mahon’s words.

At dawn the ship trembles, turns
 In a wide arc to back
 Shuddering up the grey lough
 Past lightship and buoy,
 Slipway and dry dock
 Where a naked bulb burns; (“Afterlives” 31-36)

Stanza six continues Mahon’s vivid description in which one can feel the impact of colours of dawn, lough, and bulb. Mahon chooses a very touching time, dawn time, in which a ship shakenly moves forward and backward, heading towards grey waters, a reference to death, and passing some buoys. He can only see from a distance a dock that is empty except for a bulb.

And I step ashore in a fine rain
 To a city so changed
 By five years of war
 I scarcely recognize
 The places I grew up in,
 The faces that try to explain. (“Afterlives” 37-42)

Mahon keeps describing the weather the moment he stepped ashore by saying, “a fine rain.” His own city has been changed because of the five-year war. The change can be noticed in almost everything, especially in the places he “grew up in.” he can also recognize by people’s faces how much change since he left.

This poetic reference of places is projected by Mahon to prove their importance to the reader and the speaker. Mahon includes his native Belfast, Northern Ireland, and London to show that “the troubles are treated as a further experience of belatedness ... in a melancholy poetry of place caught up, transformed and abandoned by history. Native places have been made placeless, as is the modern fate” (Brown 138). In the last stanza, all the above problems do not stop the poet contemplating his old hills. These hills are still the same from which one can have a great view of beautiful Belfast with a grey-blue colour as an indication of hope and purity. There

is a political indication in these lines as if Mahon expressed his protest to what politics and war did to his own city:

But the hills are still the same
 Grey-blue above Belfast.
 Perhaps if I'd stayed behind
 And lived it bomb by bomb
 I might have grown up at last
 And learnt what is meant by home. (Afterlives" 43-48)

Like graffiti, a worldwide protest painting, the hills colour imagery, is used to express protest against some political and social institutions almost everywhere. Thus, Mahon employs graffiti as colour imagery to denote the political tensions of his home city. In this respect, Byrne comments on such tensions and describes them as "insistent" since they are "between the colourful observable world of ordinary life and the interiorised landscape which is characteristically oppressive and neutral" (68).

Once again, the shift in pronouns, "me" to "my," is indicative of the speaker's continuing divisions. Such movement, nevertheless, becomes a source of anxiety for Mahon in "Afterlives." Returning to Northern Ireland after a time in London, the poet wonders if he had stayed in Belfast, and lived the Troubles "bomb by bomb," he would have "learnt what is meant by home" ("Afterlives" pp. 46,48).

While the rhyme on bomb/home permits the speaker's uneasiness to be disclosed, the concluding part of the poem shows its enthusiasm. The notions of "home," "place," and "space" which have filled postwar poetry in manifold ways, they also multiply being displaced or cosmopolite (Falci 200). Mahon's cosmopolitan sense is really associated with the places he visited and passed through. Regrettably, his placeless ambition and international sense lead to his feeling of exile, alienation, and homesickness.

Conclusion

To be a cosmopolite or world citizen according to Walter de la Mare and Derek Mahon, British and Irish poets, not only means to be in another place because of a promise, in the case of "The Listeners," but also to be outside one's country because of a war, in the case of "Afterlives." The main characters in both poems are travellers with different reasons and objectives. They have to take their journeys for asserting identities, keeping a promise, confirming existence, and showing their belongingness. Walter de la Mare's world is a haunted and mysterious one appealing to both the imaginative and reasonable readers who may lose themselves completely in the attractive supernatural world. On the contrary, Derek Mahon's world is a real and perceptible one which can be found in one's country or other ones.

A mere observer to nature, de la Mare believes so profoundly that all living things share the common mystery. Life, including the natural and supernatural worlds, to him, is interminably thought-provoking. With the help of the supernatural elements: ghosts, spectres, shadows, and spooky settings, de la Mare carries readers into a world, though geographically mundane, it is identifiable for its eerie atmosphere. On the other hand, Mahon is convinced that all human beings share the feelings of being estranged and homesick in other countries, though these people consider them as their new homes. In addition, he made use of different settings that arouse such feelings.

In "The Listeners," after the traveller's several questions and attempts of knocking at the moonlit door of a castle-like house, he left on his horse to nowhere. In "Afterlives," the traveller returns home voluntarily after five years, feeling homesick and patriot. Both travellers stand for all human beings for they are in a constant journey between places looking for conformity and escaping alienation as a part of their existential dilemmas. Both travellers, who are cosmopolites, are placeless, timeless, and conscious about their present and future situations. That is why their places and destinations represent homes to them. They are not restricted by their home places and regard every other place as their homes.

In the case of "The Listeners," the world citizen is not allowed to be a part of the house world, though he tries several times, possibly the traveller's world is different from the listeners' one. His efforts to communicate throughout multiple questions are faced by the listeners' unresponsive attitude. He also hopes to break the silence, unfortunately, he left in silence. As for "Afterlives," the world citizen was divided between two worlds: one is the hosting country which is regarded as a new home and the second is the original home country which is full of bombs during the time of absence.

Both poems emphasize the role of nature in comforting their main characters for it provides them with the solace that is sought during the poems. To both cosmopolites, nature, including trees, seas, animals, birds, and colourful geographical places represent home, hope, and homogeneity. Both nameless travellers stand for unknown people who move from one place to another for exploration, self-discovery, escapism, and fun. Through their journeys, travellers try to find out more about new opportunities for communication or psychological identity transformation.

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